

SOME OVERVIEW ABOUT THE PREVAIL OF THE LAW IN THE COMMUNITY

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Abstract. Absence of arbitrary power on the part of the Government, no man is punishable or can be made to suffer in body or good except for a distinct breach of law established in the ordinary legal manner before the ordinary courts of the land. This article describes some overview about the predominance of the law in the community.

Keywords: the rule of the law, accountability, open government, legislation.

The predominance of law is a principle directly related to the concepts of people's power and human rights. Because people's power means the right of citizens to directly or indirectly participate in the decision-making process. In this sense, the laws that are an expression of the people's will, adopted by the citizens through their elected representatives to the parliament or by themselves directly through a referendum, are the result, figuratively speaking, the fruit of the people's power. Human rights and freedoms are implemented through laws, in fact, the ultimate goal of laws is to protect people, their rights and freedoms. As the main elements of the prevail of law in international documents, the law-making process is based on legality, covering a transparent, accountable and democratic process; legal certainty; prohibition of arbitrariness; openness of independent and impartial judiciary; as well as the establishment of judicial control over administrative documents; respect for human rights and non-discrimination and equality before the law. Ensuring the rule of law in society, strengthening legality, reliable protection of the rights and freedoms of citizens is more urgent today than ever before. In this regard, the wide-scale reforms and specific measures implemented serve to guarantee the interests of our people. We can clearly see this in the example of the rising standard of living of people. The prevail of law is the supreme legal force of the constitution and laws in

the activities of all state authorities, and their superiority over all other regulatory documents and instructions issued by the authorities. The rule of law is a principle that serves to ensure democracy and legislation in society. According to Dicey, there must be absence of wide discretionary powers on the rulers so that they cannot make their own laws but must be governed according to the established laws. He further added “whenever there is a discretion, there is a room for arbitrariness and that, in a republic, no less than under a monarchy, discretionary authority on the part of government must mean insecurity for legal freedom on the part of the subjects.” According the principle of supremacy of law, no man can be arrested, detained, punished, or made to suffer in body or property except by the due process of law and for a breach of a law proved in the ordinarily legal manner in the ordinary courts of land. Thus at all times, the government is subject to the law and not that the law is subject to the government and its whims.

According to the World Justice Projects definition, rule of law is a system in which the following four principles are upheld. These are also known as the four universal principles of rule of law:

Accountability. The government and its officials, its agents as well as individuals and private entities are accountable under the law.

Just law. The laws are clear, publicized, stable and just; and are applied evenly; and protect fundamental rights including the security of the persons and property.

Open government. The process by which the law is enacted, administered and enforced is accessible, fair and efficient.

Access and impartial justice. Justice to be delivered timely by competent, ethical, and independent representatives and neutrals.

The state, its bodies, officials, public associations, and citizens act in accordance with the Constitution and laws". in unconditional obedience; secondly, when social relations are regulated in accordance with the interests of society, citizens and the state, and an environment of stability, order and legal order is

established at the country level; thirdly, in the prevention of violations of rights, as well as in the event that the participants of legal relations violate the law it is manifested in the performance of laws as a legal basis for prosecution in the prescribed manner. The real introduction of the principle of separation of powers in the country is an important guarantee of ensuring the supremacy of the constitution and laws. According to it, the legislative, executive and judicial branches of power operate within the framework of their powers established by the constitution and law. The supreme arbiter in harmonizing relations between them is the law.

The predominance of law allows a person to exercise his rights and freedoms without hindrance, his life, freedom, honor, dignity and other inviolable rights are guaranteed by the law to be peaceful, peaceful, calm, free from any external influences, gives the opportunity to live without fear of violence and arbitrariness. The prevail of law also allows a person to participate in the process of accepting these documents that are binding on him or through his elected representatives, to influence the state administration, to exercise public control over the activities of state bodies, his protection of rights and freedoms through the court, provides the right to appeal to the court against the illegal actions of state bodies, officials, and public associations. If the predominance of law is not ensured in society, people will lose confidence not only in today, but also in tomorrow, justice, equality and freedom will not be observed. In a society where the rule of law is not ensured, the economy will not develop, and economic reforms will not be effective. Because no one wants to bring their property and fortune to a place where the law does not work.

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